

Effect of Characteristic Total Quality Management on Performance of Health Management Performance in Tolikara District of Tolikara Regency

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ABSTRACT

Background: Measuring performance in a modern organization provides an important mechanism for employees to use in explaining performance goals and standards and motivating individual performance over time can be used for total quality management in the form of Customer focus, quality obsession, scientific approach, long-term commitment, teamwork, continuous improvement of systems, education and training, freedom of control, unity of purpose and the involvement and empowerment of employees.

Research Method: Qualitative descriptive conducted at Tolikara Hospital in May - July 2018 as many as 4 people informant. Data were obtained using interview guidelines and analyzed qualitatively.

Result of research: Carry out total quality management needed for customers, namely control, planning and improving services and the use of quality medicines. Quality obsession by working according to standard operating procedures. Approach in accordance with the main tasks and functions and solutions, the right decisions and make problems for the leadership Education and training have not been maximized in all health workers. Freedom is managed with existing rules and predetermined operational standards. Unity of purpose for the main tasks and functions is also in providing stabilization but not maximal for non-permanent employees. Challenges and empowerment of health workers are involved in providing input in improving services

Key Words: Total Quality Management, Managerial Performance, Health Employee

1. INTRODUCTION

Increasing and modern economic growth and equity will increase the needs and demands of the community for quality and affordable health services in accordance with the capabilities of the community. This is in line with the increasing ability of the community to pay for health care costs. In Law No. 36 of 2009 concerning health, it was stated that health development aims to increase awareness, willingness and ability to live healthily for each person so as to realize an optimal level of public health. The hospital must always be responsive to changes that occur quite quickly and then immediately anticipate it in accordance with the wishes and needs of the community by always referring to customer satisfaction (Customer satisfaction). Today's public demand is an easy, fast and comfortable health service, which in turn can provide satisfaction in the results of treatment in accordance with the illness. Therefore, hospitals as an organization engaged in public health services are increasingly required to provide better health services. One of the factors causing limited human resources, especially medical, is the implication of the weakness of integrated quality management. The problem of the lack of skilled employees in managing hospital services, there are still patients who feel less comfortable in their services. And this is related to the lack of optimal implementation of Total Quality Management (TQM) or Quality Management.

The phenomenon of the not yet optimal implementation of TQM, is a formidable challenge for hospital leaders and employees in Public Hospitals. The results of temporary field observations from the researchers showed that patients still often cried out the alertness of medical personnel in handling community complaints, medical personnel often delay medical treatment for a long time, there is still a lack of service facilities, as well as limited medical personnel, especially specialist doctors. So that between the expectations and realities felt by consumers or general hospital patients still need to implement Integrated Quality Management or (TQM) in order to improve the quality assurance of public health. The policy in the field of business management refers to the prospect, namely improving the quality of health services on an ongoing basis which is supported by General autonomy in all levels and work units to ensure accountability and smoothness of the hospital's competitive strategy. This policy, among others, is manifested in the efficient and effective implementation of the TQM program. Basically managerial performance is the performance of individual members of the organization in managerial activities, including: planning, investment, coordination, staffing, negotiation, and others. A person who holds a managerial position is expected to be able to produce a managerial performance. Managerial performance also needs to get extra attention from Tolikara Hospital, because currently the consument and external parties have become critical and more thorough in the use of goods or determining health services that will be the place for health services.

Tolikara Regional General Hospital is a type D hospital. Problems in hospitals from observations in May 2017 have a difference between what is expected of the patient and the reality that the patient feels about the quality of the hospital's services. We can see from a number of complaints, including the one delivered by a patient, a

patient was yelled at by his staff when asking if there might be a mistake in the results of the previous examination. Hospitals with good quality will depend on the resources available in the hospital, such as the quality of services provided by doctors, nurses, staff, and employees, as well as facilities and infrastructure available. Quality hospitals should be able to know what their patients expect because patients have the right to assess the quality of services they receive. At some hospitals still.

In addition, the problem of hospital environmental safety has not been properly considered. So that with differences in service expectations and the reality obtained will affect the level of patient satisfaction. Paying attention to the condition of the Dareah Tolikara General Hospital during the 5-year budget period, it is very interesting to know the work system in obtaining health information data from the community so that the quality of the services provided by the hospital is not quality. Measurements must be sustainable in an effort to create improvements and improve services. Based on the problem of the purpose of this study to determine the effect of the characteristics of Total quality management (TQM) on Managerial Performance of Health Workers in Tolikara Hospital.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

Qualitative descriptive conducted at Tolikara Hospital in May - July 2018 as many as 4 informants. Data obtained using interview guidelines and analyzed qualitatively.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS

Focus on customers on Managerial Performance of Health Workers in Tolikara Hospital Based on the results of the interview that in meeting the needs of patients identified from the service and planned in a meeting in improving health services to patients. Based on the results of the interview that in the ease of providing

access to services to patients by improving administrative services and ambulances for the taking and referral of patients and health workers who provide support to patients in serving patients. Based on the results of the interview that the existing health workers guarantee the safety of the patient's health by working to maintain the patient's equity and the use of quality medicines in accordance with the existing rules and guarantees of BPJS in patients. Based on the results of the interview that the existing health workers guarantee the safety of the patient's health by working to maintain the patient's equity and the use of quality medicines in accordance with the existing rules and guarantees of BPJS in patients.

Quality obsession with Managerial Performance of Health Workers in Tolikara Hospital Based on the results of the interview that the operational standard procedures have been implemented but not yet complete and some health workers are still not compliant in the implementation of standard operating procedures that exist. Based on the results of the interview, some facilities were not adequate, such as the availability of chairs and television, while the cleanliness of the room was sought by the janitor and the support of the nurses who maintained the cleanliness of the room so that the service room could provide comfort to the patient. Based on the results of interviews that hospitals try to improve patient satisfaction with existing facilities and existing facilities are still inadequate but strived optimally in meeting patient satisfaction and attention of nurses in paying attention to patients in service.

Scientific approach to Managerial Performance of Health Personnel in Tolikara Hospital Based on the results of the interview that the hospital is committed in completing the work in accordance with the existing rules that are in accordance with the main tasks and functions in each health service units and get reprimanded if it violates the rules of the direct leader such as from the head of the room. Based on the results of the interview that in making

decisions based on the special team collaboration patients who are in an emergency because of the limitations of supporting devices by doing temporary treatment to reduce the emergence and referred. This collaboration is also carried out via cellphone when in service at night the doctor is not in place. Based on the results of the interview that input to the leadership through direct submission from the supervising leaders and monthly reports that can be used as a policy in decision making.

Teamwork on Managerial Performance of Health Workers at Tolikara Hospital Based on the results of the interview, the existing collaboration is good enough to solve the problem with a conflict management approach that is expected to improve service quality. Based on the results of the interview, collaboration with other officers, especially health center staff, was intertwined quite well, especially joint activities and communication in handling patients and referrals.

Education and training on Managerial Performance of Health Workers in Tolikara Hospital Based on interviews, education and training have run optimally, especially in supporting services. Based on the interview results, the skills of employees were still found to be incompatible with the services in a particular room because the employees had not received training according to the service placement in the room.

Controlled freedom towards Managerial Performance of Health Workers in Tolikara Hospital Based on the results of interviews that each employee works refers to the main tasks and functions and emergency actions can be handled in accordance with the instructions of the doctor who had previously been given instructions, so that the existing work can be controlled in accordance with the expertise and skills of health workers.

Purpose unity towards Managerial Performance of Health Workers in Tolikara Hospital Based on the results of interviews

that each employee works refers to the main tasks and functions and emergency actions can be handled in accordance with the instructions of the doctor who had previously been given instructions, so that the existing work can be controlled in accordance with the expertise and skills of health workers. Based on the results of the interview, the commitment in payment of incentives is appropriate, including contract employees, honorariums and apprenticeships, and the amount of incentives depends on hospital income through claims from BPJS or other health insurance.

Involvement and empowerment of Managerial Performance of Health Workers in Tolikara Hospital Based on the results of the interview, it was concluded that the submission or input from other inputs that were implemented in Tolikara Hospital could work well and this was supported by the leadership who heard every complaint. Based on the results of interviews, health workers are always encouraged by the leadership in improving their performance.

4. DISCUSSION

Focus on customers on Managerial Performance of Health Workers in Tolikara Hospital The results showed that the Director and Head of the Medical Services Department were committed in providing services to patients by directing health workers to pay attention to patients, besides that the health workers carried it out well and the constraints faced were communication or language problems, especially in patients from the area. Health workers who work in Tolikara Hospital are mostly not from the local area, so communicating with customers is often a barrier. The support and commitment of officers is a very effective driving factor in the stages towards the progress of the Hospital. Tolikara Hospital relies on its customers, so it is necessary to understand the needs of current customers and the future needs of its customers, the organization must be able to meet the needs

and strive to exceed customer expectations including understanding the demographic conditions of the local area, especially how to communicate with customers. Meeting the needs of patients at the Tolikara Regional Hospital in the service of the results of interviews was obtained by identifying the services and planning in meetings to improve health services for patients. In addition, from the results of the interview, Tolikara Hospital was committed to providing easy access to services to patients by improving administrative services and ambulances for the taking and referral of patients and health workers who provided support to patients in serving patients.

Geographical conditions that are still quite difficult for the community, so that the Tolikara Regional Hospital provides an ambulance to pick up patients who have difficulties in terms of transportation in treating patients. In addition, Tolikara District Hospital has developed administrative services so that all communities can access health services. The main problem of observations in accessing services, especially patients coming from the local population, has difficulty, because not all patients have ID cards, so that with administrative services in collaboration with BPJS can be handled by Tolikara Hospital in providing health services to the community. Besides that, based on the results of the interview, the existing health workers guarantee the safety of the patient's health by working to maintain the patient's well-being and the use of quality medicines in accordance with the existing rules and guarantees of BPJS to the patient and ensure the safety of the patient's health by working to maintain the patient's patient and drug use - quality medicine according to the existing rules and guarantees of BPJS in patients. The current health care program also gets attention from the managers of the National Health Insurance (JKN). Hospitals in the application of tiered referral services in the JKN program. There are several diagnoses of patients who are not JKN participants

who can be helped by Tolikara Hospital in participating in becoming members of non-cash BPJS participants. This shows that the services provided at Tolikara Hospital are able to focus on customers in improving services.

Quality obsession with Managerial Performance of Health Workers in Tolikara Hospital The results of the study were obtained from the interviews that in improving the quality of each health worker in providing services referring to standard operating procedures that have been implemented but not yet complete and some of the health professionals. In improving the quality of service at Tolikara Regional Hospital, health personnel and hospital management still feel that they are not optimal yet, such as inadequate facilities such as chairs and television, while cleaning services have been made by the cleaning staff and nurses who maintain the cleanliness of the room so that the service room can be provide comfort to patients. In order for this to be able to support the service quality, Tolikara Regional Hospital is still in the development stage with the provision of inadequate facilities and infrastructures.

Work commitment is one of the very important factors that must be cultivated in health care providers and in the service of the RSUD, it seeks to improve patient satisfaction with existing facilities and facilities that are still inadequate but strived optimally in meeting patient satisfaction and care for nurses in paying attention to patients in service. Scientific approach to Managerial Performance of Health Personnel in Tolikara Hospital. Regulations can regulate all activities carried out by health workers and must comply because there are sanctions that violate. Regulations can be in the form of an order that binds officers to carry out service activities so that they do not deviate from the objectives, vision and mission of Tolikara Hospital. Adherence to the regulations of Tolikara Hospital by health personnel is needed to improve performance. The collaboration of

the health personnel team in making decisions is based on teamwork, especially patients who are in an emergency because of the limitations of supporting equipment by conducting temporary care to reduce the emergency and be referred. This collaboration is also carried out via cellphone when in service at night the doctor is not in place. In addition, health workers provide input to the leadership through direct submission from the supervising leaders and monthly reports that can be used as a policy in decision making.

Teamwork carried out in the continuity of services performed by health workers with existing limitations can be done with good communication between fellow health workers. This has an impact on decisions about the brand image and the quality of services that can be provided by Tolikara Hospital can be used as a strategy in achieving customer satisfaction through customer perceived value, thus demanding that hospital service entrepreneurs maintain or enhance perceived value through several indicators such as taste kinship that is able to be demonstrated, the existence of experts that are owned and the costs that must be incurred.

Strategy development can be done by involving the participation of external partners, patients, and other stakeholders. The strategy must be able to be translated widely by all internal and external components. Strategies are developed / arranged to achieve a goal through a comprehensive approach. The ability of an organization to develop strategies well will provide opportunities for innovation and as a performance benchmark that can understand the core competencies of the organization, be able to compete and collaborate with various parties now and in the future. Good strategic planning will be a change that might affect the organization's service performance, increase innovation and the ability to take advantage of diversity of opportunities, and can direct resources to be able to make priorities in dealing with health, social, ethical, regulatory,

technology, security, and other potential risks including to prevent and respond to emergencies, and other natural disasters, as well as changes in the national and global economy

Teamwork on Managerial Performance of Health Workers at Tolikara Hospital The results of the study were obtained from the results of the interview that the existing collaboration was well established with the resolution of problems with conflict management approaches that were expected to improve the quality of service. In managed organizations, competition is often created between work units within the Tolikara Hospital so that their competitiveness is boosted. However, internal competition tends to only use and consume energy which should be focused on efforts to improve quality, which in turn increases competitiveness in the external environment.

In addition to the application of TQM to improve the quality of service it is necessary

pay attention to the work discipline of its employees. Work discipline is one of the factors that can affect the quality of service as well, and is one aspect of a work system that must be considered by organizations or companies to improve company productivity, work discipline is a tool used by managers to communicate with their employees so they are willing to change a behavior and as an effort to increase a person's awareness and willingness to comply with all applicable company rules and social norms (Rivai, 2015). For this reason if there is no work discipline in achieving the company's goals it will be difficult to achieve.

Meanwhile, Tolikara District Hospital in the implementation of TQM, teamwork, partnerships and relationships was established and fostered, both between health workers and other health workers in the Tolikara District region from the results of interviews that cooperated with other officers, especially Puskesmas staff, which was quite good especially joint activities

and communication in handling patients and referrals.

Ideally, the management of Tolikara Hospital can make the accreditation status that has been obtained become an added value for the hospital, especially in establishing cooperation with various parties outside the hospital, and can be used optimally in the framework of marketing hospitals to the wider community. Accreditation status is a reason for hospitals to market hospitals to various parties, because accreditation status is a form of appreciation given by the Government to health service facilities that have met the prescribed standards (Guidelines for Hospital Accreditation in Indonesia, 2007).

Education and training on Managerial Performance of Health Workers in Tolikara Hospital The results of the study were obtained from interviews that education and training had run optimally, especially in supporting services. However, the results of interviews with health personnel skills are still found to be incompatible with the services in a particular room because the employees have not received training in accordance with the service placement in the room. This is due to the limited number of employees in providing services, so that not all employees are included in education and training. Education and training has not been optimal in Tolikara Hospital so it needs attention from management in improving the development of human resource quality in improving the quality of services with more adequate education and education. Training, it is important for health to improve productivity. The training that employees need is personal expertise in accordance with their respective jobs, so that they will get effective employees.

Controlled freedom for Managerial Performance of Health Workers in Tolikara Hospital The increase in total quality management requires the involvement and empowerment of the academic community in decision making and problem solving is a very important element. This is because

these elements can increase the 'sense of belonging' and the responsibility of the academic community towards the decisions that have been made. In addition this element can also enrich insight and views in a decision taken, because more parties are involved. Nevertheless, the freedom that arises due to involvement and empowerment is the result of planned and well-implemented control. The control itself is carried out on the methods of implementing each particular process. In this case the academic community is standardizing the process and they are also trying to find ways to convince everyone to be willing to follow the standard procedures.

Based on the results of the study that each employee works refers to the main tasks and functions and emergency actions can be handled in accordance with the instructions of doctors who have previously been given instructions, so that the existing work can be controlled in accordance with the expertise and skills of health workers. Purpose unity towards Managerial Performance of Health Workers in Tolikara Hospital Based on the results of the study from the interview that each employee works refers to the main tasks and functions and emergency actions can be handled in accordance with the instructions of the doctor who had previously been given instructions, so that the existing work can be controlled in accordance with the expertise and skills of health workers. Controlled freedom that is applied by management by establishing binding rules and international standard procedures that exist, so that health workers can work in accordance with their main duties and functions and work in accordance with existing procedures.

In improving the quality of service, the RSUD management has a commitment in paying incentives accordingly; including contract employees, honorariums and apprenticeship, and the amount of incentives depends on hospital income through claims from BPJS or other health insurance. But in reality some employees especially

employees do not remain dissatisfied with the performance that has been done. this is disbursed because of the lack of salary or wages received not in proportion to the needs or living costs in Tolikara Regency.

The conditions that occur in Tolikara Hospital for employees have experienced conditions that are generally referred to as the "comfort zone", already have a job and a fixed salary, but for employees who are not permanent it may be dismissed, work that is not far from where they live, and so on. Achievements that have been obtained by employees make no motivation to do more than what has been done.

Other results obtained from this study, provide an illustration that leadership in the Tolikara Hospital organization still lacks attention to management and social responsibility. In line with the recommendations provided by accreditation surveyors, this hospital still has not completely prepared the legal aspects related to the services provided. If analyzed further, the existing conditions show that the leadership focus is greater to improve employee performance and discipline. According to Baldrige in Ahmad (21016), leadership in organizations must not only be successful in managing and directing the organization to achieve predetermined expectations, but must carry out management and social responsibility. Management and social responsibility capabilities will guarantee the organization's ethical implementation, provide benefits to the wider community, and contribute to various Government efforts to develop community health status. Involvement and empowerment of Managerial Performance of Health Workers in Tolikara Hospital

Based on the results of the research from the interview that the submission or input from other inputs applied in Tolikara Hospital can work well and this is supported by the leaders who hear every complaint. Health workers are always encouraged by leaders to improve their performance. Concepts and methods that require

commitment and involvement of the management of Tolikara Hospital and all elements in the organization towards the organization's processing activities to consistently meet customer desires or satisfaction. In TQM it is not only the management who is responsible for fulfilling the customer's desires, but also the active role of all individuals in the organization to improve the quality of the output they produce. Employee involvement and empowerment is carried out to increase the likelihood of producing better decisions, better plans and also increase the sense of ownership and responsibility in Tolikara Hospital.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the study can be concluded as follows:

- Focus on customers on the managerial performance of health workers in Tolikara Hospital, namely the direction by management, planning and providing easy access to services and the use of quality medicines.
- Quality obsession with the managerial performance of health workers in Tolikara District Hospital by working according to standard operating procedures has been implemented but not yet complete and some health workers still lack compliance. A comfortable work environment is done quite well.
- Scientific approach to the managerial performance of health workers in Tolikara Hospital in completing committed work in accordance with the rules, main tasks and functions and sanctions for health workers and input to the leadership in order to improve service quality
- Teamwork on Managerial Performance Health Workers at Tolikara Regional Hospital are well-connected between leaders and subordinates and fellow colleagues and other officers in Tolikara Regency.

- Education and training on Managerial Performance of Health Workers in Tolikara Hospital is not optimal, because not all health workers are given the opportunity to attend education.
- Controlled freedom towards Managerial Performance of Health Personnel in Tolikara Regional Hospital in accordance with the existing rules and implementation in accordance with established operational procedures.
- The goal unity towards Managerial Performance of Health Workers in Tolikara Hospital refers to its main duties and functions and commitment to the vision and mission of the hospital.
- Involvement and empowerment of the Managerial Performance of Health Workers in Tolikara Hospital by providing input in improving services and collaboration between leaders and subordinate

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